

CogNetCare: A 5G-Based Cognitive Solution for Early Risk Detection and Continuous Monitoring

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Abstract—Cognitive health issues, such as mild cognitive impairment (MCI), Parkinson’s disease, and stroke, impact millions of people worldwide. Traditional clinical assessments often require in-person visits, which can be a barrier for those in remote or underserved areas. CogNetCare is a solution designed to bridge this gap by providing a 5G-enabled digital healthcare system that integrates remote cognitive screening and physical monitoring. This solution enables early detection and continuous tracking of neurological conditions outside traditional healthcare settings. In this paper, we introduce the system’s architecture, key performance indicators (KPIs), and validation strategies, highlighting the potential impact of such an e-health solution on real-world healthcare.

Keywords— 5G, 5GB, E-health, cognitive screening, remote monitoring, serious games, neurodegenerative disease, real-time data processing.

Introduction

5G technologies are progressively transforming healthcare, enabling remote monitoring and early intervention to be more effective than ever. CogNetCare, an innovative e-health solution, that leverages the 5G technology made available within the IMAGINE-B5G [1] SNS STREAM D project to bring cognitive and motor function assessments directly to patients, regardless of their location. The solution integrates Brain on Track, a medically certified digital remote cognitive screening tool based on serious games, and Neuro on Stride, a remote gait and motor function assessment system designed to track physical changes over time.

By harnessing 5G’s ultra-low latency, high reliability, and accurate positioning capabilities, CogNetCare ensures real-time cognitive and physical assessments for both patients and healthcare providers. Consequently, this use case contributes to advancing consumer healthcare technology by enabling widespread access to remote cognitive and motor function monitoring beyond traditional clinical settings. It also aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [2] by promoting inclusive and accessible healthcare solutions.

Despite the potential of this use case, implementing remote cognitive and motor assessments presents challenges on both medical and technological fronts. From a medical perspective, ensuring accuracy in unsupervised assessments requires robust validation methodologies and reliable data processing to ensure the medical feasibility of remote evaluations.

Technologically, achieving deterministic Quality of Service (QoS) is crucial, particularly in terms of ensuring ultra-low latency and accurate positioning, which are essential for reliable cognitive and motor function evaluations.

In this context, this paper explores the CogNetCare vertical experiment, an IMAGINE-B5G open call project, designed to validate B5G capabilities in meeting the medical requirements of the use case. The paper includes insights aiming to confirm the technical feasibility of leveraging 5G-enabled healthcare while outlining a roadmap toward a high Technology Readiness Level (TRL) comprehensive solution for remote cognitive screening and physical monitoring.

I. SOLUTION DESIGN AND SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The CogNetCare use case has emerged as part of Neuroinova’s [3] ambition’s and plan to demonstrate an e-health use case designed to integrate and operate within a high-performance 5G-enabled ecosystem that ensures real-time data exchange, and low-latency processing for a reliable cognitive and motor function assessments. The solution relies on two primary applications:

- Remote Cognitive Screening Application [3]: *Brain on Track* offers self-guided cognitive tests in the form of interactive games. By using randomized tasks, the application ensures reliable evaluations to remotely detect early signs of cognitive impairment in at-risk populations.
- Remote Physical Monitoring Application: *Neuro on Stride*, designed to track gait and fine motor function, detecting subtle changes associated with neurodegenerative conditions like Parkinson’s.

The realisation of the CogNetCare solution will rely on the portuguese experimental facility of the IMAGINE-B5G project [1]. The initial evaluation is taking place at Instituto de Telecomunicações Aveiro, using the 5GAIner infrastructure [4] based on 5G Release 17. The primary expectation from the underlying infrastructure is to provide the use case with deterministic QoS, high reliability through dynamic network slicing capabilities that guarantee ultra-low latency, and accurate Real-Time Kinematics (RTK) [5] positioning. The solution also envisions processing medical data collected from both tools at the edge of the 5G network, reducing delays and enabling real-time feedback for users and clinicians.

FIGURE 1. COGNETCARE USE CASE ARCHITECTURE

TABLE I. COGNETCARE USE CASE KPIS

KPIs	Metrics
Reliability	>99.9%
Latency	<15ms
Availability	>99%
Bandwidth	20 Mhz
Positioning accuracy	<5 cm
Throughput	16Kbps to dozens of Mbps

II. VALIDATION STRATEGY AND TRIAL ARCHITECTURE

The validation of CogNetCare follows a two-phase approach to evaluate its real-world performance in terms of network reliability, system usability, and medical accuracy. The first phase consists of controlled trials in the IMAGINE-B5G Portuguese test facility, where network slicing performance, latency stability, and edge computing efficiency are assessed under different network conditions.

The second phase involves a pilot deployment in real-world healthcare environments, including mass-screening booths and residential settings. This phase evaluates the usability of the system among healthcare professionals, patients, and caregivers, ensuring accessibility and ease of adoption. Performance analysis focuses on cognitive screening accuracy, motor function tracking reliability, and the responsiveness of the underlying 5G network infrastructure. The trials aim to evaluate *Brain on Track* and *Neuro on Stride* under different latency, throughput, and mobility scenarios, with collected data used to refine system algorithms and enhance real-time assessment capabilities.

Figure 1 describes the system architecture supporting the realization of the use case, integrating remote cognitive screening and physical monitoring within a 5G-enabled

healthcare framework. The infrastructure comprises RAN resources (pRRU, RHUB, and BBU), the 5G Control Plane, and the UPF, with a MEC server to process the cognitive and motor function data at the network edge, reducing latency and enabling real-time feedback. On the service layer, the solution incorporates *Brain on Track* for cognitive assessment and *Neuro on Stride* for motor function monitoring, with the RTK [5] providing centimeter-level positioning accuracy for precise gait analysis. The Cloud-based orchestration [6] using OpenStack [7], Open-Source Mano (OSM) [8], and OpenSlice [9] aims to support the flexible deployment and management of these network services, enabling vertical service provider and third-party developers to initially onboard these service capabilities. Ultimately, capitalizing on ITAV's built-in 5G slice manager [10], each of these services will be instantiated on a dynamically provisioned slice customized with a maximum latency for the screening and monitoring steps.

During the cognitive screening process, one of the principal measurable outcomes generated by *Brain on Track* is user response time, a variable that has clinical significance as a potential early indicator of cognitive impairment. Response time is closely associated with cognitive processing speed, executive function, and attentional control—domains often affected during the initial stages of neurodegeneration. Prior studies [11, 12] have shown that delayed reaction times are correlated with synaptic dysfunction, neuronal loss, and reductions in brain network efficiency [13]. Moreover, deviations in response time, when adjusted for demographic factors such as age and education level, may offer early diagnostic value even before classical symptoms such as memory loss become clinically evident [14]. Notably, when run remotely over digital mobile network connectivity, such as 5G, it is crucial to ensure that *Brain on Track* delivers response time measurements that accurately reflect the user's cognitive performance. Variability in network quality can introduce delays that distort these measurements, potentially

resulting in false-positive indications of cognitive impairment. For instance, a slower response time caused by unstable connectivity or limited bandwidth may be incorrectly interpreted as a sign of cognitive decline. To mitigate this risk, the use case incorporates deterministic latency correction mechanisms that isolate connectivity-induced delays, thereby ensuring that cognitive assessments remain valid, reliable, and unaffected by external network conditions.

During the monitoring step, Neuro on Stride would capitalize on the guaranteed low latency slice and the RTK server capability to transmit accurate positioning measurements. As such, by leveraging 5G Release 17 features, including deterministic QoS, dynamic network slicing, as well as the RTK positioning, the proposed architecture ensures a reliable and scalable framework for real-time remote assessments, expanding access to cognitive and motor function evaluations beyond traditional clinical environments.

III. CONCLUSION

CogNetCare promises a transformative approach to digital cognitive health, demonstrating a use case of 5G-powered remote screening and monitoring to enhance the early detection and tracking of cognitive impairments. The integration of real-time, high-precision monitoring solutions with B5G network slicing and edge computing aims to ensure that CogNetCare delivers a scalable, cost-effective, and highly accessible healthcare solution. As the project progresses through controlled trials and pilot studies, it aims to establish a new standard for remote neurological assessments, contributing to the broader field of consumer healthcare and wellbeing.

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